
A Research on Indian Startup Funding

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Abstract:

In the present decade, India is planning a vital shift in the direction of startup welcoming policies and a business-friendly or entrepreneur's environment. India is one of the fastest growing countries in terms of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurship is an essential input for economic development, creating new markets or opportunities. Currently, India is promoting entrepreneurship enthusiastically but it's a huge challenge for government as well as large population of India to create employment via startups.

This paper intention at offering an analytical overview of the boom and potentialities of startup systems in India i.e the progress made by India so far. Therefore, this research can contribute to a better understanding of the Investment and financing strategy of entrepreneurial ventures. Another important point to understand how funding changes with time is an important aspect. Currently, India is promoting entrepreneurship enthusiastically but it's a huge challenge for government as well as large population of India to create employment via startup

Keywords: *Startup, Entrepreneurship, Investment, Ventures, Employment.*

Introduction:

The Indian startup Ecosystem started in the late 1960s with the start of TCS, followed by Infosys in 1981 and others. These startups started as software services serving Indian software needs, and later expanding to exporting software services.

The dot-com era was a blessing for many startups, which included marketplaces, ecommerce and vendors. And finally, modern day startups comprised of the latest technology started around 2007-2008, and comprised e-commerce, logistics, marketplaces, and advertising startups. Startups like Flipkart (2007) and IXIGO (2008) were part of these. Currently, there are more than 5,200 startups in India putting it in the fourth spot just behind US, UK, and Israel (Nasscom, 2018), where Bangalore, Mumbai, and Delhi-NCR form 68% of start-up base with 44% foreign investments.

Being so startup friendly the country has attracted numerous numbers of investors, both national and international. Therefore a large amount of money is poured into the startup ecosystem. Also due to government support, technology boom and rise of tier-2 and tier-3 cities has boosted the startup ecosystem. Tier II Cities like Varanasi, Kochi and Indore and others have also attracted a few startups. Events like the launch of Startup India initiative, Digital India Initiative, US elections and the Indian bank note demonetization had a huge impact on the startup community in recent years. Military events like the surgical strike on Pakistan border by Indian army impacted the funding in India.

The dataset is acquired from Kaggle.com as "Indian Startup Funding. It includes columns with the date funded, the city the startup is based out of, the names of the funders, and the amount invested (in USD). This will also help to realize how big events like US elections and Indian

banknote demonetization, in this case, affect the funding of different startups.

Statement of Research Problem:

The aim of the present report is to study factors like date of funding, the city the startup is based out of, the names of the funders, and the amount invested (in USD). This study also helps to a better understanding of the investment and financing strategy of entrepreneurial ventures.

Research Methodology:

The study mostly relies on secondary data and is descriptive in its approach. The data was gathered from a diverse range of sources including journals, articles, newspapers, books and official website such as kaggle.com & the economic survey report.

Objectives:

1. To check the funding ecosystem change with time.
2. To check Top cities play a major role in funding.
3. To check startup funding & industry vertical are independent or dependent.

Analysis & Interpretation:

Figure 1: City location of startup with number of funding

Interpretation: From the above graph we observe that Top cities play major role in getting funding amount.

Figure 2: Distribution of startups across Top cities

Interpretation: From the above square plot we observe that Bangalore city attracts more number of investors followed by Mumbai & New Delhi.

Figure 3: Funding ecosystem change with time

Interpretation: Above graph shows how funding varies from one month to another.

Analysis of funds of startup in India:

- Maximum funding to a Startups is:3900000000.0
- As we can see Rapido Bike Taxi got maximum funding of 3900000000.0 USD. Now last see least funding.
- Minimum funding to a Startups is:16000.0
- Now as we can see Hostel Dunia, Play your sport, Yo Grad, Enabli and

CBS are least funded Startups i.e, 16000 USD.

- On Average Indian startups got funding of : 18429897

Aim: To check startup funding and Industry Vertical are independent or dependent.

Hypothesis:

H0: Whether a startup receives funding is independent on Industry Vertical.

H1: Whether a startup receives funding is dependent on Industry Vertical

Variable Considered:

Funding amount and Industry vertical.

Test statistics and P value:

By using software, we got the results

X-squared = 319186

Df = 799,

p-value < 2.2 e-16

Result:

Here P-value < 0.05 hence, we reject H0.

Conclusion:

This results indicate that there is statistically significant relationship between the funding amount and Industry Vertical

Findings:

1. A large no. of startups based in metropolitan cities like Bangalore & Mumbai are funded, which maybe due to the fact that talent availability is massive in these cities.
2. Rapido Bike Taxi got maximum funding of 3900000000.0 USD. Also Hostel Dunia, play your sport, Yo Grad, Enabliare least funded startups i.e. 16000 USD.
3. Technology-based startups which provide their service to the everyday consumer are very probable to get a lot of funding like Flipkart & Paytm.
4. Flipkart, Paytm, & Rapido Bike taxi are one of the most funded startups

whereas Ola Cabs and Swiggy were funded the most number of times.

5. By using Chi square test we prove that there is statistically significant relationship between the funding amount and city location. Also there is statistically significant relationship between the funding amount and Industry vertical.

Conclusion:

Indian Startup are now spread across the India. Startups in India face a variety of obstacles including regulatory obstacles in adequate infrastructure and lack of market knowledge successful business have shown that proactive masers can overcome this challenges such as performing research building strong relationship with stack holder and asking for mentorships and advice from session business owner. Indian startups have the opportunities to be highly successful and to aid in the country's economic growth.

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